

Comparison of R weight calibration packages

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Comparison of weight calibration procedures in R

This project compares several R packages that can calibrate weights to the known population totals. Weight calibration is the statistical procedure to produce the complex sample weights such that the weighted totals of certain survey variables match the known or estimated population totals (Deville and Särndal (1992)). Calibration is typically the last step in developing survey weights. Full workflows of weight creation are covered in Valliant, Dever, and Kreuter (2018) and Valliant and Dever (2018).

There are several weighting procedures related to calibration. *Post-stratification* (Holt and Smith (1979)) is the simplest computational form of weight adjustment to known population figures, in which the sample and the population are simultaneously broken down to mutually exclusive cells (compatible between the sample and the population), and the weights are ratio-adjusted so that the sum of weights in each cell is equal to the population total count in that cell. In order for the post-stratification to be applicable to multiple variables, the full cross-classification counts need to be known. This limits applicability of the procedure. First, such detail counts are rarely known, although they can be produced from population registers or list samples. Second, using multiple post-stratification variables ends up in a curse of dimensionality where the number of cells grows exponentially with the number of dimensions, and the sample sizes in each cell become impractically low.

Raking or *iterative proportional fitting* is a specific implementation of calibration in which post-stratification is applied sequentially for each variable with known *marginal* totals until weight convergence. The term RIM weighting is also used in specific social science disciplines; our understanding is that it is a synonym for raking. Details of terminology are explained in Kolenikov (2016). The raking algorithm can be considered a margin-wise optimization of a certain objective function. Deming and Stephan (1940) who are typically credited with the idea of raking with applications to official statistics thought it was a quadratic difference between the input and the output weights, but Deville and Särndal (1992) demonstrated that raking actually optimizes an entropy-type objective function (see their Case 2). Implementation of the objective function minimization allows for a considerable speed-up, but it may come at the expense of some robustness and/or flexibility.

When counts are estimated from another survey, the standard errors have to be adjusted in special ways, see Dever and Valliant (2010). None of the existing packages implement this adjustment.

The running examples will be based on the `{survey}` package Academic Performance Index (`api`) data:

```
data(api, package='survey')
```

The packages::functions compared in this handout are:

- `survey::calibrate()` (linear and raking calibration via optimization; weight trimming; control totals as vectors)

- `survey::rake()` (literal raking; control totals as data frames)
- `anesrake::anesrake()` (literal raking; weights scaled at 1; control totals as lists of named vectors, expressed as proportions)
- `sampling::calib()` (linear and raking calibration via optimization; control totals as vectors)
- `surveysd::ipf()` (literal raking algorithm implemented in `data.table`; control totals as lists of possibly named crosstabs)
- `ReGenesees::e.calibrate()` (linear and raking calibration via optimization; weight trimming; control totals as data frames with an internalized builder when the full frame is available)

Packages and functions

`survey::calibrate()`

The `survey` package is the best known package for survey statistics in R. The earliest versions on CRAN date back to 2003. The version used in this review is 4.5. Coming from the University of Auckland, the birthplace of R, biostatistician Thomas Lumley collaborated with survey statisticians Alastair Scott and Chris Wild to provide a de facto standard for survey statistics in R. There is a concise but comprehensive book accompanying the package.

```
library(survey)
```

The function `survey::calibrate()` implements the Deville and Sarndal concept of calibrated weights as the result of a constrained optimization, where the optimization target is minimizing the difference between the input and the calibrated weights, and the constraints are the calibration equations.

`survey::calibrate()` workflow step 1: create the design object with input weights

```
apisrs_svy <- svydesign(id=~dnum, weights=~pw, data=apisrs)
```

`survey::calibrate()` workflow step 2: organize the control totals

For `survey::calibrate()`, the control totals are expected to be in the form of a named vector, with names corresponding to the factor notation of the calibration variables. We will obtain the calibration control totals from the `apipop` population data. Declare the survey design object:

```
apipop_svy <- svydesign(id=~dnum, weights=~1, data=apipop)
```

The helper function `cal_names()` returns the names of the vector that `calibrate()` is going to expect. Note that `-1` removes the intercept (the sum of weights).

```
(svy_cal_names <- cal_names(~stype+sch.wide-1, apipop_svy))
```

```
## [1] "stypeE"      "stypeH"      "stypeM"      "sch.wideYes"
```

Control totals:

```
(ctotal <- svytotal(~stype+sch.wide, design=apipop_svy))
```

```
##           total      SE
## stypeE      4421 481.373
## stypeH        755  71.867
## stypeM      1018  88.506
## sch.wideNo  1072 135.596
## sch.wideYes  5122 505.669
```

Note that the calibration totals have **more** entries as `cal_names()` / `calibrate()` go through the linear models mechanics and remove the perfectly collinear variables. Here, the totals for the three categories of `stype` sum up to the population totals, as do the two categories for `sch.wide`. While `survey::calnames()` can make it explicit which control totals are to be used, `survey::calibrate()` can omit the extra categories (which may be dangerous).

survey::calibrate() workflow step 3: calibrate the object

```
apisrs_cal <- calibrate(
  design=apisrs_svy, formula=~stype+sch.wide-1,
  population=ctotal[svy_cal_names])
```

The return of `survey::calibrate()` is a `survey.design` object. Weights are incorporated as one of its components. Weights can be extracted from any `survey.design` object with `weights()`.

Raked weights can be produced by Deville-Sarndal optimization using `calfun="raking"` argument. These weights differ from the default linear calibrated weights (although for this simple case, it is hard to see what the relation between the two is):

```
apisrs_raked <- calibrate(
  design=apisrs_svy, formula=~stype+sch.wide-1,
  population=ctotal[svy_cal_names],
  calfun="raking")
bind_cols(
  apisrs %>% select(stype, sch.wide),
  linear=weights(apisrs_cal), raked=weights(apisrs_raked) %>%
  summarize(linear=mean(linear), raked=mean(raked),
    .by=c(stype, sch.wide)) %>%
  arrange(sch.wide, stype)
```

```
##   stype sch.wide   linear   raked
## 1     E       No 28.90673 28.91077
## 2     H       No 29.00474 29.00310
## 3     M       No 29.03749 29.03313
## 4     E      Yes 31.39684 31.39637
## 5     H      Yes 31.49486 31.49664
## 6     M      Yes 31.52761 31.52924
```

survey::rake()

A different function from `survey` package that performs weight calibration is `rake()`. It is built as the literal implementation of the raking algorithm, that is, the sequential post-stratification by each margin one at a time. Note that the help file `?survey::rake()` is titled “*Raking of replicate weight design*” but in fact it works with any `survey.design` objects.

survey::rake() workflow step 1: create the baseweight design object

```
apisrs_svy <- svydesign(id=~dnum, weights=~pw, data=apisrs)
```

survey::rake() workflow step 2: obtain the control totals

For `survey::rake()`, the control totals (referred to as “population margins” in the help file) are expected to be in the form of data frames with one column for each margin and one row for each category:

```

pop_types <-
  apipop %>%
  group_by(stype) %>%
  summarize(Freq=n(), .groups="drop")
pop_schwide <-
  apipop %>%
  group_by(sch.wide) %>%
  summarize(Freq=n(), .groups="drop")

```

survey::rake() workflow step 3: calibrate the object

The sample margins are specified as formulas, and the population margins are specified as data frames:

```

apisrs_raked <- rake(design=apisrs_svy,
  sample.margins=list(~stype, ~sch.wide),
  population.margins=list(pop_types, pop_schwide))

```

The task of producing consistent lists of formulas and population margins can be automated as follows:

```

pop_margins_list <- list()
sample_margins_list <- list()
for (x in c("stype", "sch.wide")) {
  pop_margins_list[[x]] <-
    apipop %>%
    group_by(!!rlang::sym(x)) %>%
    summarize(Freq=n(), .groups="drop")
  sample_margins_list[[x]] <- formula(paste0("~", x))
}
apisrs_raked <- rake(design=apisrs_svy,
  sample.margins=sample_margins_list,
  population.margins=pop_margins_list,
  control=list(maxit=500, epsilon=1e-6))

```

survey::rake() weights compare with those from survey::calibrate()

The weights are close to about 10^{-3} but not to about 10^{-6} demonstrating difference in algorithms.

```

testthat::expect_equal(weights(apisrs_raked), weights(apisrs_cal),
  tolerance = 1e-3 )

```

library(anesrake)

The package `anesrake` was written by Josh Pasek to support weight raking for the ANES survey in late 2000s-early 2010s when he was a PhD student at Stanford where ANES has been housed. The version used in this review is 0.80.

anesrake workflow step 2*: set up the control totals

There is no “step 1” of creating the base object that is needed for the `survey` package. The control totals can be calculated from census or a larger survey data by `survey`, and we have done this above. `anesrake` expects lists of vectors as control totals, where the name of the vector is the name of the calibration variable, and the names of the vector elements are the categories of that variable. Thus conversion from the control totals produced by `survey::svytotal()` involves a fair amount of wrangling.

```

library(anesrake)

# create the list of targets from anesrake from the survey ctotat
stype_inputter <- ctotat[grep('stype',names(ctotat))]
names(stype_inputter) <-
  sub('stype','', names(ctotat)[grep('stype',names(ctotat))])

schwide_inputter <- ctotat[grep('sch.wide',names(ctotat))]
names(schwide_inputter) <-
  sub('sch.wide','', names(ctotat)[grep('sch.wide',names(ctotat))])

# pass the variable names
api_inputter = list(stype=stype_inputter, sch.wide=schwide_inputter)

```

anesrake workflow step 3*: calibration

```

try( anesrake_weights <- anesrake(inputter=api_inputter,
  dataframe=apisrs, caseid=apisrs$dnum,
  pctlim = 0.0000001, verbose=TRUE) )

## [1] "Raking...Iteration 1"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 5.06646651928474"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 2"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 1.38896193614073"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 3"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 0.17624808037415"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 4"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 0.0223438296342326"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 5"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 0.00283230160688797"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 6"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 0.000359016882358953"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 7"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 4.55081747922081e-05"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 8"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 5.76851279188162e-06"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 9"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 7.31203561810112e-07"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 10"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 9.2685707553386e-08"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 11"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 1.1748606754125e-08"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 12"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 1.48923195997241e-09"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 13"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 1.88789650579224e-10"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 14"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 2.39199771101539e-11"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 15"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 3.04734015799113e-12"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 16"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 3.82249787378441e-13"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 17"

```

```
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 4.03010957938932e-14"
## [1] "Raking...Iteration 18"
## [1] "Current iteration changed total weights by 4.17443857259059e-14"
## [1] "Raking converged in 18 iterations"
```

```
summary(anesrake_weights$weightvec)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.9335  1.0138  1.0138  1.0000  1.0138  1.0181
```

There is a lot of output that `anesrake` produces, which slows it down very substantially especially if the screen needs to be scrolled. The weights created by `anesrake` sum up to the sample size.

library(sampling)

The `{sampling}` package is written by a collaborator of Yves Tille as a supplement to his “Sampling Algorithms” book. It has a basic weight calibration function to make it a comprehensive package for survey sampling and estimation, although the utility is confined to the classroom and research papers. It is not particularly user-friendly nor rich with metadata to be practical in production environments. The version used in this review is 2.10.

sampling workflow step 2*: obtain population control totals

The population totals are expected to be named vectors, in the style identical to those of `survey::calibrate()`. See Obtaining population control totals with `survey`.

sampling workflow step 3: calibration

The calibration function `sampling::calib()` returns a vector of weights. We can see that they are identical to those produced by `survey::calibrate()`, so we are not going to check any additional tabulations with them.

```
library(sampling)
apisrs_calib <- calib(Xs=model.matrix(~stype+sch.wide-1, data=apisrs),
  # the model matrix has to be created explicitly
  d=rep(1, nrow(apisrs)),
  # initial design weights have to be spelled out
  total=ctotal[svy_cal_names],
  method='linear')
expect_equal(apisrs_calib %>% unname(), weights(apisrs_cal) %>% unname())
```

library(surveysd)

The package `surveysd` is written to primarily support bootstrap variance estimation with calibrated data at Statistik Austria. It aims to combine all necessary steps for applying a calibrated bootstrapping procedure with custom estimating functions. It features some tools for nested structures that it magically names households and persons. The raking calibration function in this package is `surveysd::ipf()`, and there are built-in optimizations to run it in the bootstrap context.

surveysd workflow step 2*: create the control totals

This package expects the results of `stats::xtabs()` as inputs:

```
# targets
(ssd_stype <- xtabs(~stype, data=apipop))
```

```
## stype
```

```
##      E      H      M
## 4421  755 1018
(ssd_schwide <- xtabs(~sch.wide, data=apipop))
```

```
## sch.wide
##   No   Yes
## 1072 5122
```

The help function `?surveysd::ipf()` shows the appropriate syntax of `xtabs()` with weighted control total estimation when these have to be obtained from another survey (usually weights figure in the LHS of the formula).

surveysd workflow step 3*: calibration

As of version 1.3.1, the package has some implementation bugs. It is expected that the input is a `data.table`, but no conversion is attempted, and `library(data.table)` is not even listed as a dependence. Also, there is something strange going on with the interplay of the default bounds option and specification of the base weights.

```
library(surveysd)
library(data.table)

# calibration:
# dependence on data.table() is not announced
surveysd::ipf(
  dat=apisrs,
  conP=list(ssd_stype, ssd_schwide)
)
```

```
## Error: Check that is.data.table(DT) == TRUE.
## `Otherwise, :=, `:=`(...) and let(...) are defined for use in j,
## once only and in particular ways. See help(":=").
# bounds options are poorly protected even when aren't specified
surveysd::ipf(
  dat=as.data.table(apisrs),
  conP=list(ssd_stype, ssd_schwide)
)
```

```
## Error in surveysd::ipf(dat = as.data.table(apisrs),
## conP = list(ssd_stype, : Bounds are only reasonable
## if base weights are provided
```

With the errors fixed, `surveysd::ipf()` runs as follows.

```
apisrs_ssdipf <- surveysd::ipf(
  dat=as.data.table(apisrs),
  conP=list(ssd_stype, ssd_schwide),
  w='pw', nameCalibWeight = "ssd_rakedweight"
)
# compare to svy: minor differences
expect_equal(apisrs_ssdipf$ssd_rakedweight %>% unname(),
  weights(apisrs_raked) %>% unname() %>% `attr<-`("eta", NULL),
  tolerance = 1e-6)
```

There are minor numeric differences with the raked weights produced by `svy::calibrate(calfun="raking")` on the scale of the single precision machine epsilon.

ReGenesees

The ReGenesees package was developed at IStat, the Italian National Institute of Statistics, by Diego Zardetto, as a redesign of the `survey` package aimed at scaled performance and better behavior in production (especially with the business registers which was the primary responsibility of the developer within the agency.) For some period of time, it had to be downloaded as a binary from the agency website; it is currently available at <https://diegozardetto.github.io/ReGenesees/>. The version used in this review is 2.4. Some of the code is taken directly from `survey` package of which an acknowledgment is made. This means that ReGenesees and `survey` clash on names and methods. Yet, you cannot unload `survey` as ReGenesees relies on some of the functions from it.

```
if (!require(ReGenesees)) remotes::install_github("DiegoZardetto/ReGenesees")
quiet( library(ReGenesees) )
```

Some additional functionality of ReGenesees that is worth mentioning but is outside of scope of this study is its ability to handle the control totals from multistage samples and hierarchical population where the control totals may be obtained from the population census for the first stage of sampling and from the sampled clusters for the subsequent stages.

ReGenesees workflow step 1: create the baseweight design object

```
apisrs_rg <- e.svydesign(ids=~dnum, weights=~pw, data=apisrs)

##
## # Empty levels found in factors: yr.rnd
## # Empty levels have been dropped!
```

ReGenesees workflow step 2: create the template for the population control totals

One enhancement over `survey` that ReGenesees offers is the richer control total objects referred to as *templates*. They offer more structured and somewhat better protected way of specifying the control totals, as some internal checks are being run by ReGenesees when the template gets populated.

```
api_rg_ctotal <- pop.template(data=apisrs, calmodel = ~stype+sch.wide-1)

##
## # Empty levels found in factors: yr.rnd
## # Empty levels have been dropped!
```

ReGenesees workflow step 3: populate the template using the frame data

Availability of the frame data is crucial here.

```
api_rg_ctotal <- fill.template(universe=apipop, template=api_rg_ctotal)

##
## # Empty levels found in factors: yr.rnd
## # Empty levels have been dropped!
##
##
## # Coherence check between 'universe' and 'template': OK
```

ReGenesees workflow step 4: calibration

```

apisrs_rg_cal <- e.calibrate(design=apisrs_rg,
  df.population=api_rg_ctotal, calfun='linear')
if ( !all( weights(apisrs_rg_cal) == weights(apisrs_cal) ) ) {
  cat("Numerical differences found between survey and ReGenesees:\n")
  print( summary( weights(apisrs_rg_cal) - weights(apisrs_cal) ) )
  stopifnot( all(abs(weights(apisrs_rg_cal) - weights(apisrs_cal) ) < 1e-12 ) )
}

```

```

## Numerical differences found between survey and ReGenesees:
##      Min.      1st Qu.      Median      Mean      3rd Qu.      Max.
## -7.105e-15  0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -1.279e-15  0.000e+00  0.000e+00

```

The differences are on the scale of numeric accuracy 2.220446×10^{-16} .

Check that the totals make sense:

```
svyestatTM(design=apisrs_rg_cal, y=~stype + sch.wide)
```

```

##           Total           SE
## stypeE      4421 5.428031e-13
## stypeH       755 6.425791e-13
## stypeM      1018 2.135997e-14
## sch.wideNo  1072 5.211504e-13
## sch.wideYes 5122 4.434606e-13

```

Note that the standard errors are not identically zero as they were with `survey::calibrate()`.

ReGenesees redo step 3: control totals by hand

Let's reset the template for the control totals, and bring these in from those estimated inside `survey` (pretending these are control totals from another source – e.g. ACS for the general population calibration).

```
api_rg_ctotal2 <- pop.template(data=apisrs, calmodel = ~stype+sch.wide-1)
```

```

##
## # Empty levels found in factors: yr.rnd
## # Empty levels have been dropped!

```

```
str(api_rg_ctotal2, max.level=1)
```

```

## Classes 'pop.totals' and 'data.frame':  1 obs. of  4 variables:
## $ stypeE      : num NA
## $ stypeH      : num NA
## $ stypeM      : num NA
## $ sch.wideYes: num NA
## - attr(*, "calmodel")=Class 'formula' language ~stype + sch.wide - 1
## .. ..- attr(*, ".Environment")=<environment: R_GlobalEnv>
## - attr(*, "pop.vars.type")= Named chr [1:2] "categorical" "categorical"
## .. - attr(*, "names")= chr [1:2] "stype" "sch.wide"
## - attr(*, "var.by.term")= int [1:2, 1:2] 1 0 0 1
## .. - attr(*, "dimnames")=List of 2
## - attr(*, "calmodel.names")= chr [1:4] "stypeE" "stypeH" "stypeM" "sch.wideYes"
## - attr(*, "which.term.col")= int [1:4] 1 1 1 2
## - attr(*, "partition")= logi FALSE

```

```
pop.desc(api_rg_ctotal2)
```

```

## # Data frame of known totals for a *global* calibration task
## - Number of rows:      1
## - Number of columns:   4
## - Number of known totals: 4
##
## # The data frame structure is as follows
## ## Columns 1-4 identify known totals organized into *2 BLOCKS*
##
## - BLOCK 1 -----
## - Benchmark:           Counts of stype
## - Known totals:       3
## - Auxiliary variables: 3
## - Columns:            1-3
##
##      1  2  3
## aux "E" "H" "M"
##
## - BLOCK 2 -----
## - Benchmark:           Counts of sch.wide
## - Known totals:       1
## - Auxiliary variables: 1
## - Column:             4
##
##      4
## aux "Yes"

```

```

# copy the values over
api_rg_ctotal2[1,] <- cttotal[names(api_rg_ctotal2)]
# does it work?
identical(api_rg_ctotal, api_rg_ctotal2)

```

```

## [1] TRUE

```

References

- Deming, W. Edwards, and Frederick F. Stephan. 1940. "On a Least Squares Adjustment of a Sampled Frequency Table When the Expected Marginal Totals are Known." *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics* 11 (4): 427–44. <https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177731829>.
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